

Effect Of Positive Reinforcement Technique on Reading Achievement Among Primary School Dyslexic Children in Anambra State

Prof. Chinyelu Nwokolo ¹ & Ubadi Ngozi ²

^{1&2}Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

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Abstract

Reading is a critical challenge facing school pupils in Nigeria today, especially dyslexic children. This study therefore investigated the effects of positive reinforcement technique on reading achievement among primary school dyslexic children in Anambra State. Two research questions were posed to guide the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A Pretest, post-test, control group quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. Sixty primary dyslexic pupils were sampled for the study from a population of two hundred and forty primary school pupils. The sample consist of two groups; experimental and control. Experimental group was treated with positive reinforcement while conventional counselling was used on the control group. Coon, Waguespack, and Polk dyslexic screening Scale was adapted for the study. The scale was revalidated for this study. Internal consistency reliability estimate was conducted using Cronbach Alpha and the outcome yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.95. Data was collected and analysed using mean and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Results of this study revealed a significant effect of the treatment (positive reinforcement) on subjects' level of reading achievement. The study also revealed that gender affected pupils' reading achievement significantly with male pupils having more reduction in reading achievement than female pupils. Based on these findings, it was recommended that counsellors, psychologists, other educational related bodies should adopt the packages as techniques to increase reading achievement among primary school pupils since it has been identified as effective.

Key words: Positive reinforcement, technique, reading achievement, dyslexic children, primary school

Introduction

Reading is a developmental skill that everyone must master in order to thrive in today's culture. Reading is very important in communication, to academic success in any subject, and to open up the mind of the readers to a limitless universe of knowledge, especially in keeping up with the times and events in the current world. Reading is a vital skill for academic and professional success, according to Okoro (2013). To put it another way, teaching reading should not be taken lightly; great work should be put into the development of a child's reading competence in order to achieve reading fluency at a young age.

Reading fluency, according to Harris & Hodges (2015), is the absence of word-identification issues that can obstruct understanding in silent reading or the expression of ideas in spoken reading. Phonemic awareness and instinctive quick decoding of unknown words are two factors that affect reading fluency (Amao, 2014). It's worth noting that, because reading fluency is similar to other skill development, each child learns and improves at his or her own speed. It is usual for children to struggle with reading at some time in their lives. However, if learning to read becomes a constant struggle that causes a youngster to fall behind his peers, he may have a learning difficulty. Dyslexic is seen when correct and fluent word reading developments vary incompletely or with substantial difficulty (Nicolson & Fawcett, 2008). Children are generally classified as dyslexic when their reading achievement falls dramatically below the predicted levels of their age and schooling. Thus, dyslexic children are mostly at danger of exhibiting trouble in reading fluency.

Wolf & Katzner-Cohen (2017) have demonstrated that dyslexic children can be characterized as those with specific deficit in naming speed, and those whose learning disability stem from phonological processing deficits. Wolf and Bowers (2018) referred to this distinction as a double deficit model of reading disability. This model has led to the conjecture that positive reinforcement and multi-sensory linguistic method could be specifically tailored to address fluency deficits for those children who are phonologically aware and able to decode accurately but remain not fluent. Dyslexia is a specific learning disability that is neurological in origin and these children are characterized by difficulties with accuracy and fluency in reading, poor spelling, writing and decoding abilities.

According to Stein (2017), dyslexic children find it difficult recognizing the letters of the alphabet, struggling matching letters to sounds, such as not knowing what sounds b or h make, difficulty blending sounds into words, such as connecting C-H-A-T to the word chat, struggles to pronounce words correctly, such as saying “mawn lower” instead of “lawn mower”, difficulty in learning new words, smaller vocabulary than other kids of the same age. Trouble in count or saying the days of the week and other common word sequences and in rhyming, difficult expressing themselves clearly or structuring their thoughts during conversation, have some visual memory disorder in that they see certain letters backward and upside down such as writing letter “d instead of letter b, letter f instead of number 7”. They confuse the order of letters, such as writing “left” instead of “felt”. Trouble remembering facts, gripping a pencil, and using proper grammar. Trouble learning new skills and relies heavily on memorization, gets tripped up by word problems in mathematics, tough time sounding out unfamiliar words, and trouble following a sequence of direction.

Dyslexia have poor acquisition and use of words skills, difficulty in blending sounds into words, they suffers problem of auditory sequences and also manifest more speech and language difficulties. They have trouble finding the right words to say and struggle to understand and interpret accurately what they heard or observed. This is especially true when someone uses non-literal language such as jokes and sarcasm. The child may become unmotivated and develop dislike for school.

From the above view, many researchers such as Dhiabat and Tawalbeh (2019) examined the effect of reinforcement on the teaching of reading to children with learning disability. Morin (2017) also examined effect of Positive Reinforcement within the classroom on reading fluency of primary school dyslexic children. On the contrary, in solving the problem of reading fluency among primary school dyslexic children, techniques which encourages, increases the confident of children, creates an atmosphere of relaxation, active participation of children in constructions, designs, arts, and naturalistic play, story boards, and video footage are what is needed such as positive reinforcement.

Positive Reinforcement is a technique associated with Operant conditioning theory. According to Umezulike and Eneasator (2011), positive reinforcement is a technique by which when presented increases the frequency of the action of the organism. It means to create consequences that strengthens, facilitates or induces certain desirable behaviors. It can also be used to terminate or decrease an undesirable behaviour.

Positive Reinforcement increases the probability or likelihood of the frequency of the desirable behaviour. It can be material or non-material reinforcement. Materials reinforcement comes in form of tokens like pencils, pens, stokes school bags, while non-material reinforcement includes things like, praise, affection gestures and grades (Umezulike et al, 2011).

Positive reinforcement could be used to strengthen and sustained behaviour. For example, pupil who studies for examination and received an “A” will likely study harder for other subjects and in future because he or she is reinforced with an excellent grade or a gift of wristwatch by the parent or class teacher. There is a need to be flexible when reinforcing, since what is reinforcing for one child may not be reinforcing for another. It may therefore be needful to sample a number of reinforcers with a child in order to find the most effective one.

Statement of the Problem

Researchers have attempted to improve the reading fluency of children, particularly dyslexic students. A study for example, employed constructivism to improve dyslexic students' motivation and reading fluency. Similarly, research has also been conducted to identify the severity of dyslexic reading problems in primary school students, as well as the association between dyslexia severity and demographic characteristics. Despite these and other study efforts, these children continue to struggle with reading, and if this pattern is not addressed and reversed, it may continue to obstruct the developmental growth of dyslexic children.

There is no documented information on studies undertaken on the impact of positive reinforcement approach on improving the reading achievement of primary school dyslexic pupils in Anambra state. This is a knowledge gap that this study was designed to fill. It is therefore necessary to determine whether a positive reinforcement technique that has been shown to be helpful in the treatment of similar behavioural problems could provide a buffer for reading achievement among dyslexic primary school pupils in Idemili North, Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effect of positive reinforcement technique on reading achievement of primary school dyslexic children. Specifically, this study sought to determine:

1. The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores.
2. The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores?
2. What is the effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores will not be significant.
2. The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores will not be significant.

Method

This study adopted the quasi experimental pre-test, post-test and control group research design. This study involved Two groups of children; experimental and control groups. Those in experimental were taught reading using positive reinforcement technique while those in the control group were taught using conventional group counselling technique.

This study was conducted in Idemili-North Local Government Area of Anambra State. Idemili-North has ten towns namely; Ogidi (HQ), Nkpor, Abacha, Eziowelle, Ideani, Oraukwu, Obosi, Abatete, Uke, and Umuoji. This area has been chosen because it has a high number of school children who are identified with poor reading fluency, especially in English language. The sample of the study was 60 senior primary school dyslexic pupils. A purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the sample from a population of 240 senior primary dyslexic pupils in Idemili-North Local Government Area of Anambra State. These pupils were part of the study population identified through the use of dyslexic screening instrument (DSI).

The instruments used for this study are dyslexic screening instrument (DSI) which consists of checklists of basic neuropsychological skills designed in 1994 by Coon, Waguespack, and Polk and a teacher made reading achievement test. The dyslexic screening instruments is a rating scales designed to describe the cluster characteristics associated with dyslexia and to discriminate between the pupils who display the cluster characteristics and the pupils who do not. It is two page instruments and contains thirty two items. The instrument was rated on a five point scales, ranging from never exhibits, seldom exhibits, sometimes exhibits, often exhibits, to always exhibits. The researchers further determined the internal consistency reliability of the instrument using the Cronbach-Alpha; the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.95. The researchers visited the schools; solicit the cooperation of the school headmaster/mistresses so as to build in the programme into the schools' activities. With the principals' permission, the researcher sought the assistant of the schools Guidance Counsellors for treatment.

During the period of the treatment, the subjects for this study were assigned to two groups, one experimental group and one control group. The experimental group received positive reinforcement treatment while the control group received the conventional group counselling treatment. After the treatment, the research instruments were re-administered to the experimental and control group respectively. Data collected was collated and analysed using SPSS version 23. Mean was used in answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance.

Results

Data collected were analysed and presented in tables as follows:

Research Question 1

What is the effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores?

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest Achievement Mean Scores of Dyslexic Pupils Treated with Positive Reinforcement Technique Compared to those treated with Conventional counselling technique

Groups	No	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	Stand dev	Mean	Stand dev	
Positive Reinforcement	20	40.60	9.99	97.60	3.53	57.00
Convectional counselling	20	35.45	11.09	36.85	11.87	1.4

Table 1 showed the mean and standard deviation of achievement scores of dyslexic pupils in the two groups. The mean scores indicated that the positive reinforcement technique had a higher mean gain. Dyslexic in the control group who received conventional counselling had the least mean gain after the experiment. This shows that the experimental groups achieved more than the control group.

Research Question 2

What is the effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores?

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest Achievement Mean Scores of male and female Dyslexic Pupils Treated with Positive Reinforcement Technique Compared to those treated with Conventional counselling technique

Groups	No	Pretest		Posttest		Mean gain
		Mean	Stand dev	Mean	Stand dev	
Male	08	40.75	12.22	98.00	3.02	57.25
Female	12	40.50	8.79	97.33	3.94	56.83

Table 2 showed the mean and standard deviation of posttest mean scores of male and female dyslexic in Positive Reinforcement Technique group. The mean scores indicated that the male dyslexic pupils in the Positive Reinforcement Technique group had a marginal higher mean score than female pupils in this group. This shows that the male pupils did better than female dyslexic pupils in the Positive Reinforcement Technique group.

Null hypothesis 1

The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores will not be significant.

Table 3: ANCOVA on the effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on Dyslexic Pupils' reading achievement compared to those treated with conventional counselling

Dependent Variable: posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	pvalue	Remark
Corrected Model	46731.156 ^a	3	15577.052			
Intercept	14010.036	1	14010.036			
pretest	898.656	1	898.656			
groups	41217.801	2	20608.901	328.196	.000	S
Error	3516.494	56	62.795			

Total	395441.000	60
Corrected Total	50247.650	59

Table 3 showed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 59df denominator, the calculated F is 328.196 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores is significant.

Null hypothesis 2

The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores will not be significant.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female Dyslexic Pupils' reading achievement compared to those treated with conventional counselling

Dependent Variable: posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	pvalue	Remark
Corrected Model	3.561 ^a	2	1.780			
Intercept	10569.212	1	10569.212			
Pretest	1.427	1	1.427			
Gender	2.177	1	2.177	.159	.695	NS
Error	233.239	17	13.720			
Total	190752.000	20				
Corrected Total	236.800	19				

Table 4 showed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 19df denominator, the calculated F 0.159 with Pvalue of 0.695 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The effect of Positive Reinforcement technique on male and female primary school dyslexic pupils compared to those treated using conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest reading achievement mean scores is not significant.

Discussion

The finding also indicated that pupils in both experimental and control group had low level of reading achievement before the commencement of the treatment as measured by their scores on the pre-test. The finding also indicated that the magnitude of the mean difference between the experimental and control group was significant in the post-test. This is so, because in positive reinforcement classes, the process of learning of each child is unique. Pupils are not compared with each other and do not compete against each other, pupils are given the opportunity to learn, make their mistakes and ask questions, thereby raising the confidence in reading learning ability on improving reading achievement. Thus pupils experienced an atmosphere of peace and tranquility.

This finding is consistent with prior researches that reported that positive reinforcement technique was effective in classroom on the academic achievement of students with intellectual disabilities. The finding was also in line with Dhiabat and Tawalbeh (2019) whose finding revealed that positive reinforcement technique was effective on academic achievement of students with intellectual disabilities. The finding is also in line with Morin (2017) whose study examined the effects of inclusion and positive reinforcement within the classroom. The reason for this finding might be due to the notion that students were frequently reinforced over every expected response made. Secondly, the reinforcement (token) must

have increased the number of words correctly read on each of each trial until criterion was reached through the list of words without errors. The performance of each subject would therefore likely be more accurate and rapid in the experimental group (who receive token) than in the control group (who didn't receive token).

Findings of this study showed that there was no significant gender difference on the effects of positive reinforcement technique on reading achievement of male and female primary school dyslexic children in Anambra state. Although the reading achievement of male pupils was slightly higher than that of female primary school dyslexic children after they had participated in positive reinforcement technique treatment, the observed difference is not significant. This finding agrees with that of Lam, Yim, and Ng (2008) whose result indicated that positive reinforcement technique had more impact on males than females. Thus, it is possible that males may have yielded themselves more easily and willingly to put more effort to change their negative feeling toward reading. However, as it known the reinforcer is individual characteristic or choice since what act as reinforcer for a child may not act as a reinforcer for another child). So there is clear preference for the child as individual choice.

Conclusions

Positive reinforcement technique was effective in enhancing reading achievement among primary school dyslexic children. Also the finding of the study showed that the technique was more effective in treating male children than female dyslexic children.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. The use of positive reinforcement technique should be used by practicing school counsellors to assist primary school dyslexic children on reading achievement.
2. The use of positive reinforcement technique should be commenced in full force in primary schools in Anambra state irrespective of pupils' gender and class as a way of enhancing their reading achievement.

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